

THE IMPORTANCE OF SPORTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE YOUNG GENERATION

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Abstract: This article briefly discusses the importance of sports for a person's health and the views of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev in this regard.

Key words: Sport, physical education, healthy lifestyle, sports complex, ethnosport

The physical side of development is the basis for the mental. A healthy, prosperous and developing country cannot be built without sports.

A. V. Lunacharsky

In the first years of independence, the implementation of serious reforms in the country's economic, political and cultural processes led to the emergence of new directions of historical importance in the field of physical education and sports. Improving the health of the population, raising the physical fitness of schoolchildren and students, improving the skills of talented athletes on the basis of current requirements and international standards, as well as increasing the work skills and productivity of the working masses and intellectuals, and most importantly, life through a healthy lifestyle. Special attention is paid to prolongation and education of a healthy generation. The decision of the government of the republic "On measures for the further development of physical education and sports in Uzbekistan" has historically acquired a special place as a basic program of physical culture and sports.

On March 5, 2018, the decree of the head of our state “On measures to fundamentally improve the state management system in the field of physical education and sports” was adopted. In accordance with the decree, the Ministry of Physical Education and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established on the basis of the previous state committee and its regional divisions, and its tasks and powers were expanded.

Physical education and sports are of great importance in creating a healthy lifestyle. Therefore, on March 15, 2019, the “Humo Arena” sports complex was built in Tashkent.

According to the decree and decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 18, 2022, the Ministry of Sports Development was established. One of its most important tools is the popularization of sports among children and young people.

On April 1, 2022, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev held a meeting on measures to develop mass sports among young people. It was noted at this meeting that the goal of increasing the number of people regularly engaged in physical education and sports to 33% in the next five years is set in our development strategy.

We believe that the mutual cooperation of school, family, pedagogues, students and parents is an important tool that improves the quality of work and implements a healthy lifestyle in the daily life of students. It is important for a child to engage in physical education and sports for a healthy and well-rounded formation. The importance of physical education in strengthening human health will be explained to the students during the training. A person engaged in physical education becomes strong, agile, resistant, strong-willed, resilient, brave, beautiful and mobile. Therefore, he tries to perform every action independently, well and with little effort. According to historical sources, the national sports and national games of the Uzbek people varied depending on the living conditions of the population and prepared people for active and productive work. In this regard, it is no coincidence that

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed the decision “On popularization and development of ethnic sports”.

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